

Internal Friction and Mechanical Properties of Dispersion-Strengthened Iron

A. G. Mikeladze, F. N. Tavazde

Institute of Metallurgy, Academy of Sciences of the Georgian, Tbilisi, 380048, USSR

ABSTRACT

A technology has been developed to obtain cast samples of iron with particles of Al_2O_3 of dispersity not more than (3-6% vol) distributed homogenously in the matrix. Surface-active elements (< 1 % w) were used as doping material.

The samples were investigated by means of internal friction method. It was shown that the magnitude of deformation caused by dispersed particles was 2-3% and that interaction of dislocations with dispersed particles began in the limits of microplastic deformation.

Ansell-Lenel model is suggested to explain strengthening mechanism of matrix. Homogenous distribution of dispersed particles which do not accumulate preferably on the defects provides free work of dislocation sources to obtain plastic deformation. Such material can be strengthened preserving plastic properties of matrix.

INTRODUCTION

Artificially introduced dispersed particles which do not interact with matrix up to the melting point give the material with combination of properties inachievable in the classical alloys.

Strengthening can be obtained and plastic properties preserved by right selection and homogenous distribution of high dispersity second phase. However it is rather hard technological task. Insoluble usually more light particles come to the surface of the melt. It is necessary that the matrix material wet the particles which must remain insoluble at the same time.

As we know, wetting of solid body by liquid is determined by Physical (Wandervaals) and chemical forces. Surface tension of the most of metals is $\sim 10 \text{ erg/cm}^2$.

Interaction energy of the same order is necessary for wetting process. Physical forces can't provide such an energy, therefore, chemical interaction is necessary also.

Liquid metals do not wet refractory metallic oxides well. However, some metals capable to create ions with great charge must wet ceramic surfaces better because of the electrostatic interaction (1). The metals chemically active to O_2 , such as pure Ti, Zr, Cr and their alloys form little contact wetting angles with surfaces of oxides of the type of Al_2O_3 , BeO and others(1).

EXPERIMENT AND DISCUSSION

In the Institute of metallurgy the technology was developed to obtain cast samples of iron and its alloys with particles of Al_2O_3 of dispersity not more than 1μ (3-6% vol) homogeneously distributed in the matrix. The alloys were doped by surface-active elements (1% w).

The charge was melted in the electron arc melting furnace in the specially constructed copper watercooled crucible where the mould was placed for casting the rods of 4 mm in diameter and 120 mm in length.

The matrix material was iron containing C not more than 0,3% w and Cr - 0,1 + 0,8 % w. According to quantity of Cr the quantity of particles of Al_2O_3 was 3-6% vol.

Investigations show that dispersed particles essentially strengthen the material preserving its plasticity. On discussing the strengthening mechanism the most of the scientists are based on the Orovan model where the moving dislocations pass between the particles without destroying and deforming them leaving dislocation loops. According to Orovan criterion the tensile strength is defined as the stress necessary to bend dislocation loops around the particles and it is inversely proportional to the distance between the particles, λ . Equation for Orovan's stress is given below

$$\Delta\sigma = \frac{G_m \cdot b}{\lambda} \quad (1)$$

Where G_m - shear modulus of matrix, b - magnitude of Burgers' vector, λ - distance between the particles. In our case $\lambda = 0,8-1$. The value of tensile strength of the investigated dispersion-strengthened material determined by the model is much significantly lower than that determined by experiments.

The results are well explainable by the model of Ansell and Lenel (2). This model takes into account interaction of the leading dislocation with elastic fields of the residual loops. In order to provide microdeformations in correspondence to tensile strength it is necessary the included particles to be destroyed or deformed by the concentration of shear stresses caused by dislocation pile-ups around the particles.

In this case

$$\Delta\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{G_m \cdot G_p \cdot b}{2 \lambda C}} \quad (2)$$

where G_p -elastic modulus of dispersed particles.

C -constant depending on the perfection degree of crystal lattice of particle ($C \approx 30$).

Interaction between matrix and dispersed particles was investigated by means of low temperature internal friction method. The arc-melted cast rods (without intermediate treatment) were mounted in the relaxator and the temperature and amplitude dependence of internal friction were measured. Frequency of measurement was 2-5 Hz. Measurements were held in constant magnetic field of 500 Oe in order to eliminate the effect of magnetomechanical hysteresis and magnetic aftereffect. The results of temperature dependent measurements are given in fig. 2.

Dispersed particles reveal broad well-reproducible maximum at 200°C. The maximum is of relaxation-type. Temperature of the maximum increases up to 60% upon increasing the frequency of measurements from 2 to 4 Hz. Activation energy calculated after this shear is equal to 1,2 eV. Annealing decreases the maximum but can't annihilate it.

The observed maximum in dispersion-strengthened iron (fig. 2 curve 2) is analogous to the maximum in deformed iron and martensitic steels (3). Such a maximum can be due to formation of martensitic phase or to matrix deformation. The first possibility is eliminated because the content of C in our samples is not more than 0,3% w. In such cases martensitic maximum is not noted. So, the maximum can be due to matrix deformation only. Analogous peak in deformed iron is known as Koster effect. Proper treatment of the data gives the possibility to compare the height of the maximum with the degree of plastic deformation. The height of the maximum in dispersion-strengthened iron corresponds to the degree of deformation of order 2-3%.

Possible sources of matrix deformation can be the stress due to significant difference in coefficients of thermal expansion of particles and matrix and besides, the phase clench and interphase stresses due to transformation on the matrix-particle boundary. It seems, that magnitude of deformed sections depends on the degree of matrix-particle wetting factors. The results of amplitude-dependent internal friction measurements are given in fig. 3, 4, 5.

Generally, amplitude-dependence is connected with energy scattered by moving dislocations. At low tensions, (up to ϵ_{c21}) internal friction does not depend on the amplitude. It is the section of elastic deformation only. The increase of the amplitude above ϵ_{c22} , leads to increase of energy scatter. It is supposed that the curve of amplitude-dependent internal friction bends in accordance to the degree of dislocation pinning by interstitial impurity atoms (fig. 3, 4).

Subsequent increase of the amplitude (above ϵ_{c22}) leads to significant nonreversible increase of internal friction e.g. to microplastic deformation (fig. 5).

Measurements show that introduction of dispersed particles increase the leaning angle of amplitude-dependent internal friction and decrease ϵ_{c21} , (fig. 3, 4). The value of activation energy calculated by the leaning angle at different temperatures is 0,5 eV. The value is in accordance to interaction of dislocations with interstitial atoms, in particular with C. Therefore, one may conclude that dispersed particles enlarge the quantity of dislocations without interaction with moving dislocations in the limits of inverse deformation (up to ϵ_{c22}).

Decrease of values of ϵ_{cz_1} and ϵ_{cz_2} in dispersion-strengthened samples is also the evidence of increased density of dislocations. It appears that dispersed particles increase not only the quantity of dislocations in the metal volume but at the same time the length of moving dislocation segments

Scattering of oscillation energy connected with dislocations relaxed from oxygen atoms is more intensive under the applied stress than that in the samples without dispersed inclusions.

Increase of amplitude above ϵ_{cz_2} (fig. 5) leads to significant irreversible increase of internal friction. In this range of amplitudes leaning angle of the curve of dispersion-strengthened material qualitatively differs from the curve of matrix. It seems interaction of dislocations with dispersed particles begins within the limits of microplastic deformation.

Homogenous distribution of dispersed particles without preferable accumulation on defects in the volume of metal provides the free work of dislocation sources and leads to plastic deformation giving the strengthening of the material preserving plastic properties of the matrix.

REFERENCES

1. Naidich Iu.W. "Contact Phenomena in metallic melts". Naukova Dumka, Kiev, 1972, p.70.
2. Ansell G.S., Lenel F.V. "Criteria for Yielding of Dispersion-strengthened alloys" Acta Metallurgica, vol.8, № 9, 1960. p.612.
3. Van Bueren H.G. "Imperfections in Crystals" Amsterdam, 1960, p.319.

Fig. 1. Mechanical properties of cast samples at room temperature. The velocity of deformation is 1 mm/min.
 Curve 1. Starting material-iron containing $C \approx 0,0,2\%w$.
 Curve 2. Iron containing Cr-0,6%w
 Curve 3. Iron containing Cr-0,4%w and Al_2O_3 -3% vol.
 Curve 4. Iron containing Cr-0,8% w and Al_2O_3 -6% vol.

Fig. 2. Temperature dependence of internal friction
 Curve 1. Starting material-iron containing
 $C \approx 0,0,2\%$ w.
 Curve 2. Iron containing Cr- 0,8% w and
 Al_2O_3 -6 % vol
 Curve 3. Iron containing Cr-0,8 % w

Fig.3. Amplitude dependence of internal friction
 Curve 1. Starting material-iron
 Curve 2. Iron containing Cr-0,8%w and
 Al_2O_3 -6% vol.

Fig. 4. Amplitude dependence of internal friction of dispersion-strengthened sample at different temperatures

Fig. 5. Amplitude dependence of internal friction at high amplitudes of measurement
 Curve 1, Starting material-iron
 Curve 2, Iron containing Cr-0,8%w and Al_2O_3 -6%vol.

